

1 Analyses of sublittoral macrobenthic community change in a marine nature reserve
2 using similarity profiles (SIMPROF)

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25 HIGHLIGHTS

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27 Macrofaunal data from the Skomer Marine Nature Reserve (MNR) in Wales are

28 analysed

29 Samples are from 6 sublittoral surveys spanning 16 years, from 1993 to 2009

30 Type 1, Type 2 and Type 3 Similarity Profiles (SIMPROF) analyses are used

31 Large changes in species composition occurred, particularly between 1993 and 1996

32 Sediment changes, perhaps driven by storms, appear to drive variation among

33 species

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36 Keywords: Ecosystem change, Marine parks, Nonparametric multivariate analysis,

37 Time-series, Similarity profiles

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39

40 ABSTRACT

41 Sublittoral macrobenthic communities in the Skomer Marine Nature Reserve
42 (SMNR), Pembrokeshire, Wales, were sampled at 10 stations in 1993, 1996, 1998,
43 2003, 2007 and 2009 using a Day grab and a 0.5 mm mesh. The time series is
44 analysed using Similarities Profiles (SIMPROF) tests and associated methods. Q-
45 mode analysis using clustering with Type 1 SIMPROF addresses multivariate
46 structure among samples, showing that there is clear structure associated with
47 differences among years. Inverse (r-mode) analysis using Type 2 SIMPROF decisively
48 rejects a hypothesis that species are not associated with each other. Clustering of
49 the variables (species) with Type 3 SIMPROF identifies groups of species which
50 covary coherently through the time-series. The time-series is characterised by a
51 dramatic decline in abundances and diversity between the 1993 and 1996 surveys.
52 By 1998 there had been a shift in community composition from the 1993 situation,
53 with different species dominating. Communities had recovered in terms of
54 abundance and species richness, but different species dominated the community.
55 No single factor could be identified which unequivocally explained the dramatic
56 changes observed in the SMNR. Possible causes were the effects of dispersed oil and
57 dispersants from the Sea Empress oil spill in February 1996 and the cessation of
58 dredge-spoil disposal off St Annes Head in 1995, but the most likely cause was severe
59 weather. With many species, and a demonstrable recovery from an impact,
60 communities within the SMNR appear to be diverse and resilient. If attributable to
61 natural storms, the changes observed here indicate that natural variability may be
62 much more important than is generally taken into account in the design of
63 monitoring programmes.

64 **1. Introduction**

65 With an area of 13.24 km², the Skomer Marine Nature Reserve (MNR) surrounds
66 the island of Skomer (Fig. 1), the smaller islands of Middleholm and Gateholm, and
67 parts of the Marloes Peninsula in western Wales, UK. Water conditions range from
68 relatively sheltered, deeper, waters north of the Marloes Peninsula, to shallow
69 waters subject to extremely strong tidal currents. The waters and shores around
70 Skomer Island have a long history of marine biological investigation, although few
71 studies are reported in the peer-reviewed literature. Bassindale (1946) primarily
72 described littoral communities around Skomer, although some sublittoral species,
73 collected in dredgings from North and South Haven, were recorded. Hunnam (1976)
74 provided some information on sublittoral infauna around Skomer, and a series of
75 surveys in the 1980s mapped littoral and sublittoral habitats within the reserve
76 (reviewed in Bunker and Hiscock, 1987). Following an initial quantitative survey of
77 benthic communities in 1993 (Rostron, 1994) a subset of stations from this survey
78 was selected for on-going monitoring (Fig. 1). These were quantitatively sampled in
79 1996, 1998, 2003, 2007 and 2009 (Rostron, 1997, Barfield, 1999, 2004, 2008, 2010).

80 Within a very widely-used framework for the nonparametric multivariate analysis
81 of ecological data, Similarities Profiles (SIMPROF) analysis was described by Clarke et
82 al. (2008) as, primarily, a way of testing for multivariate structure among samples.
83 Recently Somerfield and Clarke (2013) demonstrated how Similarity Profiles analysis
84 and other approaches may be combined to analyse associations among species, and
85 to visualize those relationships. Type 2 SIMPROF determines whether observed
86 associations could have arisen by chance. Type 3 SIMPROF detects statistically
87 distinct subsets of species which respond to gradients in a coherent manner. How

88 different groups respond is visualised using component line plots (coherent curves).
89 The aims of this study are to use the various types of SIMPROF and associated
90 methods to explore temporal variation in the benthic communities around Skomer
91 over this 16 year period, and to consider the causes of observed changes.

92

93 **2. Materials and methods**

94 *2.1 Field sampling*

95 Although full details of the sampling and sampling analysis are given in the
96 relevant reports (Rostron, 1994, 1997, Barfield, 1999, 2004, 2008, 2010) they may be
97 briefly summarised as follows. Samples were collected in late autumn (October to
98 November) using a 0.1 m² Day grab. Single samples were collected from 19 stations
99 in 1993. 10 of these stations were selected for resampling in 1996 to represent a full
100 range of variation in sediments and conditions (Fig. 1), when 2 or 3 replicate
101 samples were taken. In later surveys (1998, 2003, 2007, 2009) 2 replicate samples
102 were taken from each of the 10 stations. Large, readily visible organisms were
103 picked out of each sample on deck, and the remaining sample was sieved on a 0.5
104 mm mesh and preserved in formalin for later analysis. A further grab was taken for
105 sediment grain-size analyses.

106

107 *2.2 Laboratory analyses*

108 Animals in the samples were counted and identified to the lowest possible
109 taxonomic unit (generally species). Quality control procedures, such as blind
110 comparisons of samples, were generally conducted within later surveys and a
111 reference collection of voucher specimens was maintained.

112

113 *2.3 Numerical analyses*

114 Samples collected from stations only sampled once, in 1993, were excluded from
115 the analyses presented here. Prior to analysis taxa that were not identified to
116 species, or that were only found as juveniles, were omitted. Replicate samples were
117 pooled, so the numerical values in the data matrix are abundances of organisms 0.1
118 m⁻². Following a rigorous taxonomic standardisation, using taxonomic hierarchies
119 from the UK Marine Species Directory (Howson and Picton, 1997) and the European
120 Register of Marine Species (Costello et al., 2001), datasets were merged within the
121 PRIMER package (Clarke and Gorley, 2006).

122 For Q-mode (sample) analysis abundances were fourth-root transformed and
123 used to calculate Bray-Curtis similarities between every pair of samples. The
124 resemblance matrix was clustered using hierarchical agglomerative clustering, and
125 the resulting divisions tested using Type 1 SIMPROF. The matrix was visualised using
126 non-metric multidimensional scaling ordination (MDS).

127 The focus of this paper is on temporal patterns in the MNR as a whole, so prior to
128 inverse (r-mode) analysis abundances of each species were averaged within years.
129 Variables were reduced by selecting only those species contributing at least 2% of
130 total abundance in any one year. Annual abundances of each of the selected 33
131 species were standardised (converted to percentages of the total abundance of each
132 species). A between-species resemblance matrix was constructed using the Index of
133 Association (Sommerfield and Clarke, 2013). The Index of Association (IA) takes the
134 value 100 when two species have exactly the same percentage abundances across
135 the samples (full positive association) and the value zero when they are found in

136 completely different samples (full negative association). Defining y_{ij} as the
137 abundance of the i th species ($i = 1, \dots, p$) in the j th sample ($j = 1, \dots, n$),

$$138 \quad IA = 100 \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{y_{1j}}{\sum_{k=1}^n y_{1k}} - \frac{y_{2j}}{\sum_{k=1}^n y_{2k}} \right| \right]$$

139 Type 2 SIMPROF was used to determine whether species were associated with
140 each other in terms of their numerical variation through the time-series. Species
141 were clustered using hierarchical agglomerative clustering, and the resulting
142 groupings tested using Type 3 SIMPROF to determine whether groups of species
143 covaried coherently. Coherent curves (component line plots) were constructed to
144 visualise how groups of species vary through time.

145 The analyses presented here were conducted using a developmental version of
146 Primer 7 ($\alpha 8$), though all analyses may be undertaken using Primer 6 (see Somerfield
147 and Clarke, 2013 for details).

148

149 **3. Results**

150 *3.1 Variation in faunal composition among years, Q-mode analysis*

151 38458 organisms belonging to 683 species were retained in the dataset following
152 data reduction. Type 1 SIMPROF confirms that there is significant multivariate
153 structure among samples. Close examination of the dendrogram (Fig. 2) indicates a
154 major division among sites at a similarity of 25-26%, which corresponds to a division
155 between samples from > 20 m (to the left) and those from < 20 m (to the right).
156 Within groups of samples for which Type 1 SIMPROF fails to reject a hypothesis of
157 multivariate structure there is a tendency for samples from individual years to be
158 clustered, rather than samples from individual sites. Ordination by MDS (Fig. 3)

159 shows that samples from the 1993 and 1996 surveys stand out as being different
160 from the rest, and the remaining surveys (1998, 2003, 2007, 2009) lie very close to
161 each other. In general station-to-station differences in community structure were
162 retained across years (Fig. 3), although there is a marked shift in community
163 structure at Station 1 between 2003 and 2007. Since this corresponds to a known
164 relocation of this station owing to sampling difficulties in 2007, data from this station
165 are omitted from the following analyses.

166 Temporal patterns in part reflect variation in abundance and species richness (Fig.
167 4). There was a dramatic decline in abundance between the 1993 and 1996 surveys,
168 though average abundances had recovered by 1998. There was a less marked
169 decline in numbers of species between 1993 and 1996, but a marked increase in
170 species richness between 1996 and 1998, with the higher level of species richness
171 being sustained in later surveys.

172

173 *3.2 Taxa contributing to variation in faunal composition among years, r-mode* 174 *analysis*

175 Having established differences between years it is important to understand the
176 nature of these differences in terms of the taxa involved. Type 2 SIMPROF assesses
177 whether there are more, or less, species associated with each other (covarying) than
178 would be expected if occurrences were essentially random. The results (Fig. 5) show
179 that the observed value of π (4.3) is well outside the range of values which could
180 have arisen if the null hypothesis, of no association among species, were true. Thus
181 associations among species are significant. The Type 2 similarity profile (Fig. 5)

182 shows that there is an excess of both lower-than-expected values of the IA (negative
183 associations) and higher-than-expected values (positive associations).

184 Clustering of the species, with Type 3 SIMPROF tests at each node (Fig. 6),
185 identifies 5 groups of species (A - F) which covary coherently among years. Coherent
186 curves (Fig. 7) display these different patterns of variation. Species in Type 3
187 SIMPROF group A were relatively abundant in 1993, declined or disappeared by
188 1996, and showed at best only limited recovery in following years. Species in group
189 B increased dramatically between 1993 and 1996, disappeared by 1998 and
190 remained absent or only present in low numbers in following years. Group C consists
191 of the single species *Abra alba*, which appeared in numbers in 1998, declined to
192 lower numbers by 2003 but persisted in following years. Fluctuations in relative
193 abundance of species in group D are characterised by variable abundance early in
194 the time series, low abundance in 1998 and 2003, and then increasing abundance
195 through 2007 and 2009. Species in group E were continuously present from 1998
196 onwards, generally increasing in abundance, while species in group F were absent in
197 1996 before increasing to a dramatic peak in abundance in 2007 from which they
198 subsequently declined.

199 These variations in percent abundance may, in part, be explained by observed
200 variations in sediment composition (Fig. 8). Species in group A (e.g. *Chamelea*
201 *striatula* and *Ampelisca tenuicornis*) are typically found in finer sediments, and it is
202 clear that the major change in sediments between the 1993 and 1996 surveys was a
203 decline in mud (silt and clay) content, and a shift to coarser sand and gravel. The
204 increased sandiness of the sediments persisted in all the subsequent surveys.
205 Species in group B (e.g. *Balanus balanus*) are typically found on coarse or mixed

206 substrates, reflecting the peak in gravel content in 1996 (Fig. 8). *Abra alba*,
207 constituting group C, is known to recruit in large numbers, which apparently
208 happened in 1998, perhaps in response to space being made available by the decline
209 in the coarse sediment fraction and the generally sandier nature of the sediments.
210 Group E species are typical of clean sands, though the slow increase in species'
211 percentage abundance may reflect increasing sediment stabilisation and increasing
212 habitat heterogeneity. For example, *Sabellaria spinulosa* is a potential stabiliser of
213 sediments, *Pisidia longicornis* is known to be associated with *Sabellaria* reefs, and
214 *Pomotoceros lamarcki* requires substrata such as shell on which to settle, though
215 *Mediomastus fragilis* and *Nephtys kersivalensis* are more indicative of mobile clean
216 sands. Species in group D are more likely to be found in mixed sediments such as
217 stable shelly gravels. For example, *Pholoe inornata* inhabits empty shells, while
218 *Dipolydora caeca* burrows within them. *Opiothrix fragilis* and *Kurtiella bidentata*
219 indicate finer sediment, and it is possible that observed interplay between the clay
220 and gravel content of the sediments (Fig. 8) reflects variation of abundance within
221 this group. Species in group F (e.g. *Sphaerosyllis hystrix* and *Ampelisca diadema*) are
222 also commonly found in sands, though the similarity in pattern with the clay content
223 of the sediment (Fig. 8) is striking. These species were absent in 1996, so it is
224 possible that the changes in sediment structure between 1996 and 1998 facilitated
225 recruitment, and presence of clay in the sediment represents a proxy for sediment
226 stability.

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230 **4. Discussion**

231 Similarity Profiles (SIMPROF) analysis has a number of uses in the analysis of
232 ecological community data (Clarke et al., 2008; Somerfield and Clarke, 2013). Here
233 we show how Type 1 SIMPROF may be used to test hypotheses concerning structure
234 among samples and may be useful in providing a stopping rule for interpretation of
235 divisions imposed by a clustering algorithm. Type 2 SIMPROF (Somerfield and Clarke,
236 2013) assesses whether observed associations among species should be interpreted
237 and indicates the nature (positive or negative) of those associations, while Type 3
238 allows the detection of coherently varying species. Coherent curves are used to
239 visualise these coherent patterns in variation. We believe that these methods are a
240 significant advance on other techniques, such as Similarity Percentages analysis
241 (Clarke, 1993), used to examine variation among species (variables) and how this
242 variation contributes to differences among samples. The major finding of the
243 analyses conducted here are that major changes occurred in macrobenthoc
244 communities inhabiting sediments within the Skomer MNR between surveys
245 conducted in 1993 and 1996, assemblages shifted to a diverse but different state by
246 1998, and since then have remained relatively stable albeit with shifts in relative
247 abundance of various species.

248

249 *4.1 Possible causes of large interannual changes in faunal composition*

250 Major storms battered the Skomer MNR in the weeks preceding the 1996 survey
251 (Rostron, 1997). Waves > 12 m high with a period of 15 s were reported on October
252 28. The factors determining sediment disturbance at depth by wind waves at
253 specific sites involve a complex interplay between exposure, depth of the water

254 column, tidal currents, sediment composition and surface roughness and biotic
255 interactions (Hall, 1994), but it is likely that forces at the seabed were very
256 destructive during the storm, at least at shallow sites (Rostron, 1997), leading to the
257 observed major changes in community composition and sediment structure. That
258 the sediments lost much of their mud content (Fig. 8) is consistent with the idea that
259 fine sands may have been brought into the area by wave-driven resuspension and
260 transport (Rostron, 1997), as is the fact that species in type 3 SIMPROF group A are
261 those that typically inhabit muddy sediments. For example, it is known that among
262 the tube-building Ampeliscidae all prefer poorly sorted sediment but different
263 species have differing preferences, with *A. tenuicornis* preferring sediments with >
264 16 % mud (Parker, 1984).

265 Rees et al. (1977) described large changes in benthic populations and associated
266 alterations in sediment silt-clay content associated with storm events in shallow
267 waters on the northern coast of Wales, and storms have been shown to have marked
268 effects on benthic community structure in similar communities elsewhere (e.g.
269 Grémare et al., 1998, Labrune et al., 2007, Posey et al., 1996, Van Hoey et al., 2007).
270 The removal of *Ampelisca abdita* tube mats by winter storms is part of the annual
271 cycle in community structure off parts of the eastern coast of North America (Mills,
272 1969). Many amphipods, including Photidae and Ampeliscidae, are tube dwellers
273 and their presence may enhance sediment cohesion and stability, and provide
274 habitat for some species while excluding others (Mills, 1969). As mentioned above,
275 the increasing trend in the percentage abundance of *Sabellaria spinulosa* may also
276 have contributed to increasing sediment stability following the shift to sandier

277 sediments in 1996, supporting the increase in percentage abundance of associated
278 species.

279 Two other possible causes of observed patterns of variation merit consideration.
280 On February 15, 1996, the tanker Sea Empress, laden with 131,000 t of crude oil and
281 2,400 t of heavy fuel oil, ran aground on rocks at the entrance of Milford Haven, only
282 12 km or so from Skomer. Over a period of time 72,000 t of crude oil and 360 t of
283 fuel oil were released into the sea. Although much of this was dispersed into the
284 water column by dispersants sprayed from the air, a sheen/oil mixture spread over a
285 wide area, and quantities of oil came ashore within and adjacent to the MNR. Being
286 winter, and during a period of high winds, the water column would have been fully
287 mixed, and once oil was incorporated into the water-column it would easily have
288 reached the seabed. High sediment loads of total hydrocarbons (up to 355 ppm)
289 were found in North Haven (Station 4) on April 2, but levels consequently fell
290 (Rostron, 1997) and there is little evidence of any long-term (months to years)
291 presence of elevated hydrocarbons in sediments within the MNR (Moore, 2006).

292 Among the species in Type 3 SIMPROF group A that declined or disappeared
293 between 1993 and 1996 was *Ampelisca tenuicornis*. Ampeliscids are considered to
294 be susceptible to oil pollution (Gesteira and Dauvin, 2000) and intolerant of even
295 very low concentrations. Following the Amoco Cadiz spill ampeliscids disappeared
296 from contaminated sediments and were slow to recolonize (Cabioch et al., 1982;
297 Dauvin, 1982). Studies of benthic communities closer to the Sea Empress spill
298 around Milford Haven (Rutt et al., 1998) showed reductions in abundances of
299 amphipods and cumaceans, but no other notable effects on the macrofauna, or
300 evidence of sustained contamination. The effect under consideration here is a

301 general one, effecting almost all species and groups of species, so while the effects
302 of the oil spill may be part of the explanation we consider this unlikely.

303 The Sea Empress incident was a very public affair, appearing on national and
304 international news programmes and in other news media daily for weeks. Less
305 public was a change that took place in 1995. As in most ports catering for large
306 vessels, maintenance dredging is necessary to maintain navigable channels within
307 Milford Haven and its approaches. Up to 1995 maintenance dredgings, primarily
308 consisting of fine sediments, were regularly discharged at a disposal site 5 km or so
309 off St Anne's Head, only 10 km southeast of the MNR. In 1995 the site was closed,
310 and since then dredgings from Milford Haven have been taken to a new site some 20
311 km to sea for disposal. In 1993 many sites within the MNR had relatively high
312 proportions of mud in their sediments, compared to later years (Fig. 8), which could
313 reflect the cessation of import of fine material derived from dredgings, either as bed
314 load or as suspended load. Thus the observed changes in assemblages could in part
315 reflect longer-term changes driven by management decisions made some distance
316 from the MNR.

317

318 *4.2 The consequences of large changes in the context of monitoring*

319 The trajectory of changes observed at Skomer suggests a single severe event
320 followed by recovery. Storm-driven changes in community structure represent only
321 one aspect of on-going natural variation. Interestingly, the changes observed at
322 Skomer are similar in scale, extent and timing to changes observed in an *Abra alba*
323 community off the coast of Belgium (Van Hoey et al., 2007). Using a more extensive
324 time-series they demonstrated that large-scale shifts in community structure, lasting

325 several years, could be related to biological (recruitment) and physical (storms,
326 sediment changes, cold winters) factors. Even in the absence of extreme events, the
327 spatial structure of benthic communities may be highly variable (Armonies, 2000).
328 Thus it may be that there is no need to seek a particular cause for observed
329 variation, as it may simply reflect the natural ecological dynamics of the system. Few
330 monitoring programmes take such potentially extreme variation into account in their
331 design. As seen here, it is often impossible to unequivocally assign observed changes
332 to potential causes of change, especially when those causes operate on spatial scales
333 as large as, or larger than, the spatial extent of the monitoring survey. The idea that
334 benthic communities are stable and persistent over long periods, in shallow
335 sediments at least, is probably no longer tenable, and large shifts in community
336 structure from one year to the next should not be considered surprising.
337 Acknowledgement of such variability, however, is currently lacking within many
338 marine conservation management frameworks. The purpose of monitoring in such
339 frameworks is generally to determine measures and see if they are consistent with a
340 target, or 'baseline' conditions. If they are, conservation objectives are being met
341 and the feature being monitored may be considered to be in favourable status. As is
342 shown here, variation of >50% in some measures may be entirely natural, which
343 makes deciding what the baseline is, and detecting departure from it, potentially
344 problematic. That being said, the Skomer MNR has consistently been shown to be in
345 good condition and delivering its conservation objectives, despite the shifts in
346 community structure described here.

347

348 *4.3 Recovery, resilience and sediment monitoring in the Skomer MNR*

349 It should be noted that the Type 2 and Type 3 SIMPROF analyses presented here
350 are based on average community composition across the entire MNR in each survey.
351 The Type 1 SIMPROF analysis (Fig. 2) shows that there is much more rich structure to
352 explore, and a sensible next step in a full analysis might be to employ Type 3
353 SIMPROF within depth groups (> or < 20m for example), or indeed for individual
354 stations, to explore temporal and spatial patterns.

355 The results presented here indicate that the sediment monitoring programme
356 around Skomer is fit for purpose, as it could identify major changes in community
357 structure and provide information about the nature and extent of such changes. The
358 macrofaunal communities around the island are diverse, and resilient. It is to be
359 hoped that the time-series will be maintained, not only to detect the effects of major
360 events in the future but also to gain a better understanding of natural variability, and
361 the biology of species, within these communities. Good quality benthic time-series
362 are extremely rare and valuable, and where they have been maintained for 20 years
363 or more they become important research tools (e.g. Dauvin, 1998, 2000, Frid et al.,
364 2009, Warwick et al., 2002). Given that one of the stated goals of marine nature
365 reserves is to provide opportunities for study and research, the maintenance and
366 enhancement of this benthic infaunal time-series is a worthwhile activity above and
367 beyond simply monitoring the state of the environment.

368

369

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479

480 FIGURE LEGENDS

481

482 **Fig. 1.** Map of Skomer Marine Nature Reserve (MNR) showing sampling stations.

483

484 **Fig. 2.** Dendrogram derived by hierarchical agglomerative clustering with group-
485 average linkage from Bray-Curtis similarities calculated from fourth-root transformed
486 species abundances at each station averaged within years. Solid lines indicate
487 significantly different samples and groups of samples ($p < 0.05$), dashed lines indicate
488 groups of samples for which the null hypothesis could not be rejected ($p > 0.05$), as
489 identified by Type 1 SIMPROF. Numerals indicate stations, symbols indicate years.

490

491 **Fig. 3.** Ordination by non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS) of samples based
492 on Bray-Curtis similarities calculated from fourth-root transformed abundances of
493 macrobenthic taxa at each station averaged within years, labelled to highlight
494 differences among years (symbols) and stations (numerals).

495

496 **Fig. 4.** Variation in within-station average numbers of individuals per 0.1m^{-2} (N) and
497 numbers of species (S) in samples. Means \pm 1 s.d. plotted against the years in which
498 data were collected.

499

500 **Fig. 5.** Type 2 SIMPROF test based on index of association among the subset of 33
501 species which each contribute at least 2% to the average abundance in any one year.
502 The observed value of the statistic π (4.3) falls outside the distribution of values
503 generated by 999 permutations representing null-hypothesis conditions and is

504 therefore highly significant ($p < 0.001$). In the Similarity Profile continuous lines
505 denote the observed profile, the full set of pairwise resemblances ordered from
506 smallest to largest (y axis) plotted against their rank (x axis). Dashed lines are limits
507 within which 99% of resemblances would be expected to fall, for any given rank,
508 under the null hypothesis of no association amongst species.

509

510 **Fig. 6.** Dendrogram from (r-mode) group-average clustering of the 33 'most
511 important' species, based on the Index of Association among species, as in Fig. 5.
512 Continuous lines indicate the 5 'coherent groups' (A - F) which were significantly
513 differentiated by Type 3 SIMPROF tests (at the 2% level). Within each of these
514 groups, the null hypothesis that all pairs of species have the same association to
515 each other cannot be rejected, the subgroup structure identified by cluster analysis
516 thus having no statistical support (dashed lines).

517

518 **Fig. 7.** Groups of 'coherent curves', namely component line plots for the groups of
519 species identified in Fig 6, showing the consistency of species responses within
520 groups. The y axes are percentages of the total abundance of each species found
521 across the 6 surveys (i.e. 'species-standardised', untransformed data). Species
522 within groups are not individually identified because of their statistically inseparable
523 responses.

524

525 **Fig. 8.** Line plots of average percent contribution of different sediment fractions
526 across years.

HIGHLIGHTS

Macrofaunal data from the Skomer Marine Nature Reserve (MNR) in Wales are analysed

Samples are from 6 sublittoral surveys spanning 16 years, from 1993 to 2009

Type 1, Type 2 and Type 3 Similarity Profiles (SIMPROF) analyses are used

Large changes in species composition occurred, particularly between 1993 and 1996

Sediment changes, perhaps driven by storms, appear to drive variation among species

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

